

EXTENSIBLE PHYSICAL OCEANOGRAPHIC REAL-TIME SYSTEM (PORTS)

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I. ABSTRACT

NOAA's PORTS is a decision support system to facilitate safe and efficient maritime commerce and effective environmental resource management. PORTS is installed in Tampa Bay, New York/New Jersey Harbor, Houston/Galveston, and San Francisco Bay. PORTS consists of real-time observations of ocean conditions and weather, computer model nowcasts and forecasts of ocean fields, and dissemination of data via a telephone voice data response system and Internet.

PORTS information ensures that an adequate margin of safety is available to larger and larger ships in channels which are being deepened but not significantly widened. PORTS provides information permitting shippers to load their vessels to take full advantage of real-time water levels and channel improvements. PORTS information guides hazardous materials spill prevention and response as well as effective ecosystem health management.

The San Francisco Bay PORTS is the model for a future National PORTS. That model is an extensible PORTS based on an Information Hub Concept (InfoHub) which will permit PORTS to adapt to evolving user needs. The extensible PORTS provides standard sensor interfaces to encourage the addition of non-NOAA sensors to the system. A data base provides a broad user community with access through downloadable applications and applets on Internet. PORTS provides information broadcast to shipboard vector and raster Electronic Chart and Information Display Systems and a Lockheed Martin/Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute Navigation and Piloting Expert Systems (NPES). An open architecture design will encourage commercial and academic partners to participate in National PORTS development.

II. INTRODUCTION

The National Ocean Service (NOS) of the National Oceanic

Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) has stewardship of the nation's ocean resources. That responsibility requires NOS balance the needs for an ecologically healthy marine environment with economically productive use of marine resources and the safety of the half of the American population now living near the coasts. The mission of NOS is to provide information, data products and services, and to apply scientific understanding to:

- Manage and conserve the nation's coastal and marine environment;
- Promote safe and efficient marine and air navigation; and
- Observe, assess, and predict changes in the coastal and global ocean.

The safety of people, the health of the marine environment, and the efficiency of maritime commerce go hand in hand. The safety of people depends on the accurate prediction of oceanic and atmospheric conditions. Storms annually take their toll on people both at sea and in low lying communities. Spills of hazardous materials from maritime accidents threaten the lives of nearby residents and destroy natural marine habitats. Maritime accidents not only threaten public safety and a healthy environment but constitute an enormous economic burden on the cost of transporting goods in and out of our ports and harbors. The value of goods passing through US ports and harbors now exceeds \$500 billion per year. Modern ports are very competitive commercial operations where information upon which rational decisions to balance safety, health of the environment and commercial viability of the coastal community must be made.

NOAA and its predecessor organizations have had the responsibility for a century and a half to provide information for safe and efficient navigation of the nation's waters. This responsibility has extended in recent decades to include the rational management of marine resources from head of tide to the exclusive economic limit two hundred miles offshore. In an increasingly competitive global marketplace tradeoffs must

be made between economic interests and preservation of the environment. NOAA's dual role is no more present than in ensuring the safety and efficiency of maritime commerce.

III. EXISTING PORTS

PORTS has expanded from Tampa Bay, which began operation in 1991, to now include Houston/Galveston and two NOS Partnership Project demonstration systems: NY/NJ Harbor and SF Bay.

Two needs for PORTS were identified in Tampa Bay (Frey 1991): "improving the margin of safety for moving petroleum products and highly hazardous liquid sulphur and anhydrous ammonia in tankers and barges; and achieving economic benefits by onloading additional phosphate products when higher-than-usual water levels allow." Of primary consideration was the fact that ship's pilots aboard vessels must have ready access to real-time data. That access was provided through a telephone voice data response system.

The popularity of the Tampa Bay PORTS prompted calls by pilot's associations, port authorities, the shipping industry, and environmental resource managers for similar systems in other ports and harbors. That call was first met in NY/NJ harbor. The channel between the Kill Van Kull and South Newark reach was deepened but not significantly widened in recent years. As a result, larger vessels with limited maneuvering ability were transiting the 120° turn at Bergen Point. The USCG VTS quickly recognized the need for a special area regulation which gave the vessel with the following current the right of way in the turn. However, the most accurate information available was NOAA's Tidal Current Tables which were known to have 95% confidence intervals for flood, ebb and slack times of 90 minutes. The variance in the timing and strength of tidal currents is due to natural variability in freshwater flows to Newark Bay, which have been reported to be so strong at times that the tidal current does not flood for several days, and to weather driven anomalies in the currents. A demonstration PORTS for NY/NJ Harbor was installed and provides the real-time current information in support of USCG VTS special area regulations as well as providing water level sensor integration into a centralized data acquisition and dissemination system at the USCG VTS Center on Governor's Island, NY. NOAA still maintains this PORTS demonstration, but is looking for partnerships with the user community to maintain it after October 1, 1997.

The Houston/Galveston Navigation Safety Committee (HOGANSAC) was instrumental in providing support to install a PORTS in Galveston Bay and approaches. A narrow ship channel traverses the Bay nearly north-south. This channel is used by both deep draft vessels requiring every inch of channel depth and shallow draft barges. The shallow draft barges outnumber the deep draft vessels by roughly ten to one. The shallow draft vessels are especially vulnerable to changes in the wind driven flows in the Bay which result in large changes in water depth and current conditions. PORTS was installed to provide information so the barge and deep draft traffic can more safely share the deep draft channel. As the channel improvement projects planned for the near future are

completed it is anticipated that PORTS will provide information which will permit establishment of a wider real-time fairway for shallow draft vessels when water levels permit. Current meters and water level gauges with meteorological sensors are located at Morgan's Point, Red Fish Bar, and Bolivar Roads. The Houston/Galveston PORTS is operated and maintained under an agreement between NOAA and Texas A&M University, Galveston.

A second PORTS demonstration project was established in San Francisco Bay in response to a need in the Upper Bay for real-time information to support coastal resource management decisions about the fresh water supply to restore endangered fisheries nursery grounds and ensure safety of oil transport. The California Department of Water Resources (CDWR), the US Geological Survey, and NOAA joined to provide data to determine the location of the 2 PSU salinity line. The areas with salinity less than 2 PSU are sufficiently fresh to restore the fisheries nursery for endangered species such as the Chinook Salmon. The information obtained in this partnership enables the State of California to supply just the needed amount of fresh water, a precious commodity, during just the right seasons. In addition to the salinity sensors, the initial PORTS demonstration project included current measurements at the Benecia Bridge near docking facilities for two major oil terminals in the upper Bay and a water level system with meteorological sensors near Port Chicago. The project has since been expanded to serve the needs of the maritime commerce industry in the central Bay with current and water level systems with meteorological sensors in the vicinity of the Richmond Longwharf, the Golden Gate Bridge, and the Oakland Bar Channel.

IV. EVOLVING NEEDS FROM THE SF BAY DEMONSTRATION PROJECT

San Francisco Bay and the Delta comprise a rich and diverse coastal ecosystem. Draining over 40 percent of California, they comprise the largest estuary on the West Coast. The Bay supports both a commercial salmon industry and six major ocean shipping ports serving container terminals, oil refineries and petroleum-blending facilities. Unfortunately, urban, suburban, industrial development have reduced significantly the quality and quantity of the Bay's aquatic habitat. Together, these factors create management challenges that must be addressed if the Bay is to maintain its maritime economy and its rich, but stressed, natural resource base.

In partnership with the Bay Conservation and Development Commission (BCDC), NOS's coastal management partner in San Francisco Bay, shipping interests, including the Port of Oakland, the Harbor Safety Committee, and Marine Exchange, and others, NOS has developed the San Francisco Bay Demonstration Project to:

- Support the expansion of the Bay area's maritime economy while the Bay's ecological resources are protected and managed for the future; and
- Set in place new ways of doing business between local communities and NOS that will result in more effective and efficient operations.

The San Francisco Bay Demonstration Project is based on three major principles: local focus, local involvement, and efficiency of coastal resources decision support. The key issues identified included:

- More efficient navigation;
- Safer maritime commerce;
- Improved dredging operations;
- Sustainable wetland management;
- Enhanced spill preparedness;
- Response to military base closures; and
- Stepped-up monitoring of contamination.

In response to these issues, NOS launched expanded activities in the following areas:

- PORTS to improve coastal resource management and navigation efficiency and safety (prevention and response to hazardous spills);
- Electronic charting systems to improve navigation safety;
- Nautical chart improvements, including digital products, to support electronic charts and improve navigation safety;
- Coastal Geographic Information System (GIS) framework to unify all resource management information for the Bay;
- Photogrammetry to establish new regulatory boundaries and shorelines for nautical charts;
- Convert to GPS based datums for greater accuracy and long term stability;
- Update Environmental Sensitivity Indices (ESI) used in spill response;
- Improve distribution of hydrographic data through use of a GIS; and
- Organize regional contaminant databases into one common format.

The local community, through this project, has established needs for new ways to access this information. PORTS has been identified as the ideal information hub to integrate the marine environmental information and disseminate it to a diverse local user community. NOS is working toward implementation of a PORTS Information Hub (PORTS InfoHub) which has the extensibility to meet future evolving user community needs.

V. REQUIREMENTS FOR EXTENSIBILITY

The evolving needs for PORTS flowing from the SF Bay Demonstration Project imply requirements for an extensible PORTS in the following categories:

- Plug and play standard interfaces to sensors;
- Universally accessible information on standard personal computer systems;
- Information analyzed and synthesized for context specific decision support;
- Industrial strength architecture and implementation;
- Open standards based design to stimulate valued added product development; and
- Process quality assurance to stimulate commercial

partnerships in a National PORTS development.

The initial PORTS installation in SF Bay was based on a partnership in which NOAA, USGS, and CDWR installed similar sensors to monitor the extent of freshwater in the Upper Bay. It has since become apparent that there would be an advantage to all partners if all the sensors shared a common interface definition so that their output could be plugged into PORTS. This type of development will require a cooperation with vendors of the sensors. The "plug and play" concept is the result of standards based computer interfaces to peripheral devices such as printers and storage media. Plug and play standard sensor interfaces would greatly reduce the effort by other Federal and State agencies to provide real-time environmental data in the Bay.

Universal user accessibility on standard personal computer systems suggests that at least two major functions must be provided: search of the information for what the user requires and dissemination in a form the user desires. This suggests that PORTS information should be provided in a standards based Open Geographic Information System context which allows searches according to a wide variety of information attributes. Universal accessibility also suggests that the user should not be required to possess any special hardware or software to be able to find, download, or view any PORTS information.

VI. PORTS INFORMATION HUB ARCHITECTURE

The development of PORTS is based on the evolution of the PORTS concept (Frey, 1991; Bethem, 1991; and Appell, 1991). PORTS will continue to support past requirements. However, the evolution of new requirements has initiated development of a PORTS Information Hub Architecture (Figure) for SF Bay as a prototype of the National PORTS. Existing PORTS consists of water level, current, and meteorological sensors at several locations (Frey, 1991). Data is collected, stored and transmitted by radio from equipment on navigational platforms. The data is received at the data acquisition site and stored on an IBM PC computer. The computer makes a subset of the data available on a display screen as text information and passes it along to a voice data response computer. Public users can dial in using a rotary telephone and request specific information. The PORTS Operations at NOAA headquarters accesses the data acquisition computer via Internet to download all data, perform quality control, and archive for retrospective study. This data is then available to the world via Internet on a World Wide Web page (<http://www.ceob.nos.noaa.gov>) and via file transfer protocol, ftp.

The PORTS InfoHub Architecture recognizes several new subsystems: a database server with OpenGIS and SQL interfaces, a decision support server, a file management server, and a World Wide Web server. NOAA is developing the Continuous Operational Real-Time Monitoring System (CORMS) to quality control PORTS and other real-time data. It will interface to the local InfoHub and a National PORTS Database which will replicate the local information. CORMS must be able to fuse data from many sensors to determine if they are physically consistent.

SF PORTS Information Hub Architecture

Existing PORTS Data Acquisition Subsystems (DAS) provide environmental data in a standard file format. These data files can be downloaded by users to their own computers. However, there is little software available which can be used to search or view portions of the data set. NOAA has recognized that not only observations, forecasts and nowcasts from PORTS would be available on the PORTS InfoHub, but a wide variety of geographically based information in support of the Demonstration Project. NOAA is working with the OpenGIS Consortium to establish a OGIS implementation for information within the San Francisco Bay Demonstration Project. The OpenGIS framework has three main parts:

- Open Geodata Model which defines a general and common set of basic geographic information types that can be used to model the geodata needs of more specific application domains, using object-based and/or conventional programming methods.

- OGIS Services Model which defines the set of services to 1) access and process the geographic types defined in the Open Geodata Model and 2) provide capabilities to share geodata within communities of users who use a common set of geographic feature definitions and translate between different communities of users that use different sets of geographic feature definitions.
- Information Communities Model which employs the Open Geodata Model and the OGIS Services Model to establish a way to efficiently maintain a common set of geographic features or at least share geodata with dissimilar sets of geographic features.

OpenGIS, coined by Kenn Gardels of UC Berkeley, was the result of an effort by a number of academic researchers in the SF Bay area. Its origins and concepts lend well to the SF PORTS InfoHub requirements for geographic based

information.

Existing PORTS provides little or no problem context specific decision support. That means that the user must learn to interpret the PORTS data in order to make an expert decision. Rather than develop a solution for every decision support problem, NOAA anticipates providing guidance to users or vendors of value added decision support products as to what kind of decisions could be supported by the PORTS information. An example of this is a partnership among Lockheed Martin, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute (RPI), Chevron Oil Company, and NOAA to demonstrate the Maritech Smartbridge™ integrated bridge concept aboard the CHEVRON COLORADO in San Francisco Bay in 1997. RPI is developing the Navigation and Piloting Expert System (NPES) which will utilize shipboard sensors, expert knowledge in navigation and piloting, and real-time environmental information from NOAA's PORTS to provide decision support on the ship's bridge. NOAA is not only defining interfaces to PORTS information for broadcast to the ship, but also providing guidance as to the validity for using PORTS data for NPES decisions.

Real-time data dissemination from PORTS has in the past largely been limited to a subset of the full data set collected from the sensors. PORTS is being enhanced to provide all data in real-time. However, it still remains the user's responsibility to turn that data into information. NOAA envisions its PORTS role as the "Earth Systems Agency" as the provider of the integrated environmental situation. That integrated situation picture will be accomplished using data fusion and analysis tools based on the idea that the atmosphere and oceans obey well known laws. It is anticipated that in the near future non-NOAA real-time sensors will input their data into PORTS further expanding coverage and the need for an integrated view.

Decision points are seldom restricted to sites where PORTS has real-time sensors. The SF Bar Pilots Association polled members of the Harbor Safety Committee for the location of decision points where currents, water levels, and weather information were needed. The result was a map of the Bay provided to NOAA by CAPT Carl Bowler with over two hundred decision points. It was apparent that the number of decision points far exceeded the practical number of PORTS observation sites. NOAA's answer is the use of computer hydrodynamic models to interpolate between sensor sites in a dynamically consistent manner to provide area coverage. NOAA funded the USGS in Menlo Park, to extend their model of the Bay circulation, water levels, and density to nowcasting and eventually short term forecasting for specific decision support contexts. The model uses real-time wind fields generated by a meteorological model as forcing. It will eventually include real-time runoff and offshore water levels.

Existing PORTS have been developed with a limited decision support community in mind. That community is the navigation safety community. As a result, PORTS injects information into the work environment of organizations responsible for navigation safety, primarily pilot associations and the USCG VTS and Marine Safety Offices. NOAA has been supplying special purpose computer hardware and

software to such sites to meet their needs. But this has created two problems: keeping up with changes in the computer technology and broadening access. The answer being studied as part of the Information Hub is that PORTS will focus on providing information servers which can be accessed by any general purpose personal computer which run common World Wide Web browsers. This information server would provide all the user information search and viewing capabilities to the user in real-time (either through downloading or interactive applets). NOAA would no longer have the responsibility for maintaining the configuration of systems at user sites, but would only have to maintain upgrades to the port central InfoHub site. NOAA has extended the Maritech SmartBridge™ integrated bridge agreement with Lockheed Martin to include the development of a prototype SF Bay PORTS InfoHub.

Development of the National PORTS is beyond the fiscal and personnel resources of NOAA at the present time. NOAA is discussing agreements with commercial enterprises to provide the expertise to make PORTS truly extensible. NOAA is also seeking partnerships for value added products based on PORTS information. NOAA will continue to support PORTS through its mission to "provide information, data products and services, and to apply scientific understanding" to earth systems.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The PORTS system was developed by the National Ocean Service to provide environmental observations and predictions in real-time to facilitate maritime commerce. The evolution of requirements from an ever expanding coastal resource management and maritime commerce user community in SF Bay is driving the development of an extensible PORTS including an InfoHub which will provide open access to PORTS developers, information providers, and users alike.

VIII. REFERENCES

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